

The *Still* Unashamed Accompanist...

Tips on becoming a collaborative artist

How do you become a collaborative pianist (a.k.a. “accompanist”)? Why would you or your students care to do so? Many years ago, the famous English pianist Gerald Moore coined the phrase the “unashamed accompanist.” In those good old days, the pianist often was hidden behind a wall of potted palms which effectively obscured nearly everything center stage but a bit of the piano and the featured artist. All of the audience’s focus was drawn, visually as well as aurally, to the “soloist.” One hopes that things have improved a bit since then!

What are some of the skills that aspiring pianists need to become successful in the field? Facile sight-reading is absolutely essential, but it is not enough. Collaborative pianists also must be able to learn music very quickly and accurately. Consequently they also must have thoroughly reliable techniques in order to cope with the enormously varied, frequently difficult repertoire they are asked to perform.

What is life like for an ensemble pianist? Most are masters at keeping their travel agents busy! Unexpected phone calls might offer them the opportunity of flying to a distant city to perform a difficult program the following night. Most people going on a trip wonder what to put in their suitcases. We wonder if we have enough time to practice the program at least once, take care of technical issues, and arrive at our destination able to concentrate intensely for the one all-too-brief rehearsal we will have before the concert!

It certainly helps if the pianist has a good sense of humor. You never know when you’ll arrive at a concert hall to discover several keys missing in the middle of the piano! My colleagues have shared hilarious tales of piano benches collapsing during a performance, music racks falling off, pianos falling through the stage floor, and page-turners dropping the music in their laps.

As teachers, how do we identify the student with potential as a collaborative artist? A pianist might be successful in this profession if, in addition to possessing all of the attributes mentioned above, he/she also has the following:

- an ability and interest in working with others
- level-headedness
- determination
- responsibility
- a well-rounded mind
- an interesting personality
- a keen imagination
- a flexibility of attitude, mind, and ear
- the ability to play with conviction, imagination, and individual expression
- a background in languages
- an extra-strong work ethic

Why would anyone choose to go into this field professionally? You probably will not be surprised to learn that for many of us the reasons are remarkably similar. The vast repertoire of the collaborative pianist means that life can always be exciting and challenging. For example, one can play a program of violin sonatas one evening, and the next night be partnering a singer in a song recital. We are lucky to work with a wide variety of interesting people. Those with whom we make music constantly feed us interpretive and technical ideas. Every colleague, in effect, becomes a teacher. We must develop and maintain our own musical conceptions about the repertoire while being flexible enough to accommodate the partner of the moment. There also is a very real fascination in working with people of different musical and spiritual minds.

What is it about ensemble performances that capture the attention of an audience? Perhaps the very human and personal interaction necessary to making music with others allows the concertgoer a glimpse into the process of creation. The audience notices when the ensemble is uncanny. Inevitably there is something special about such keen collaboration. It is this level of interactive music making that every ensemble artist of my acquaintance hopes to experience. It is the reason that many pianists are drawn to the field during their school days and beyond.

How can you guide students whom you believe have a chance at collaborative careers? Encourage and mentor them. Take them to “live” concerts. Urge them to study other languages. Discuss recent books you’ve read, or poets whom you admire. Make opportunities for them to accompany their singer colleagues or their friends who play orchestral instruments. Above all, notice their enthusiasm and support their choice. If they love the repertoire, thrive on the experience, and simply can't imagine doing anything else, then perhaps their future has found them!

Do my colleagues and I believe that we made the right career choice? Absolutely!
Would we recommend our niche of the profession to young artists? Without question!
Is it worth it? We cannot imagine doing anything else!

Written by Jean Barr, National Chair of Collaborative Performance, for the American Music Teacher magazine - October/November 2000.